

RESTRUCTURING AND ORGANIZATIONAL DEVELOPMENT: INTERROGATING THE KEY FACTORS FOR ADVANCING EQUITY AND INCLUSIVENESS

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Abstract: *Restructuring in the organization has taken the top burner in academic debate. This has become imperative in order to strengthen organizational efficiency and service delivery. Therefore, this study examined key factors that should be taken into considering when transforming the organization. The study adopted qualitative research method. Factors like team building, employee empowerment, capacity building, leadership and automation were properly interrogated. The study concluded that organizational restructuring is one of the most challenging periods for any organization, whether public or private organization. It is therefore imperative that the leadership is mindful of this, and ensure the deployment of all the factors that we have enunciated and interrogated to create room for efficient and positive restructuring outcome.*

1. Introduction

Organizational restructuring is a strategic process of altering an enterprise's internal structure such as reporting lines, team roles and department functions to improve operational efficiency, adapt to market/service demands, or support long-term growth of

Organizational restructuring cuts across a wide range of areas. Essentially, it involves embedding diversity, equity, and inclusion (DEI) into the core of the organizational structure. It replaces performative policies with concrete, systemic changes in reporting lines,

resource allocation, and decision-making to ensure fair opportunities, representation and equitable outcomes for all employees. As the organizational environment becomes increasingly complex and more subjected to frequent changes, a need to change the organization's structure and adjust elements of the existing structure becomes imperative (Johan and Ukpere (2012, Ugorji E , 2024, Ifeanyidike and Chukwuemeka, 2024) . Leaders are thus challenged with the demand to introduce various changes during the transformation of their organizations'

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structures. The design of an organizational structure capable of withstanding the needs of modern businesses has been one of the most challenging issues facing modern organizations and their leaders.

It is imperative to note that restructuring is not limited to business organizations, it also applies to the public sector organizations.

Restructuring implies that inclusion must be recognized. But today most organizations are restructured and neglect inclusiveness. In other words they fail to carry the employees along in order to give them sense of belonging.

2. Organizational Restructuring and Team building

Team building is the continuous process of turning a group of individual employees into a cohesive, cooperative unit. It uses daily interactions, formalized strategies, and

collaborative activities to nurture mutual trust, align workers under share goals, and ultimately drive workplace productivity, service delivery and satisfaction

The Acronym ‘TEAM’

The acronym ‘TEAM’ can be summarized as follows: T for together, E for Everyone, A for achieve and M for More. (Together everyone achieve more). Team building therefore is helping people to understand that they are greater collectively than individually. It is an understanding that all of our decisions will be better when some degree of collaboration is applied. It is bringing people to a place where there is an honest appreciation of each other’s essence ... where they come from.... Where they have been. Because in this appreciation is the driver for collaboration.

Fig 1: *Team building*

Characteristics of team work process

- (a) Common goals
- (b) Interdependent
- (c) Common operating procedure

- (d) Accountable

Common Goals

A team must be focused on achieving common goals. Although this seems very straightforward, team members often do not have a common

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understanding or level of commitment to organization and team goals.

Goals of a team must be:

- clear and explicit
- motivating and challenging
- tied to rewards in order for a team to reach a level of maximum performance.

Interdependent

Team members must rely on each other to get the job done. Interdependence in a team context means individual members recognize that each member brings unique skills, experience, and perspective which are needed to accomplish team goals. In addition, team members must understand the value of group processes and how group processes maximize productivity.

To achieve interdependence, team members must:

- understand team goals and how they relate to the goals of the organization
- be committed to team goals and
- demonstrate a willingness to solve individual and team problems.

Common Operating Procedure

Teams must have common operating procedures in order to accomplish tasks. This means that team members have established formal and informal systems, procedures, processes and norms for addressing the various issues facing the team. Agreed procedures reduce conflict and problems within the team by ensuring efficient and productive processes.

Accountable

Each member of a team must be held responsible for producing specific outputs and results. There must be a clear delineation of roles and responsibilities within a team for

members to be held accountable. As a team matures, a high level of ownership develops among members in which individuals take on a variety of responsibilities that cross over role boundaries.

Common Team problems

- unclear goals
- low commitment
- misunderstanding of jobs or roles
- failure to utilize team members talent
- guarded communication
- failure to share information
- poor meeting
- one person decision
- conflict within team
- amount of time to make decision
- low confidence in others
- criticism and complaining
- distinct subgroups

Organizational restructuring should be able to address the problems listed above.

Components of good Team Process

- Clarity in team goals
- Clearly defined roles
- Clear communication
- Well defined decision procedures
- Established ground rules
- Balance participation and
- Improvement plan

Teams which strive to improve and refine these components will reach high levels of team performance than those teams who neglect some or all of these components.

3. Interplay between Leadership and Organisational Restructuring

Organisational restructuring is a seismic shift that hinges entirely on the quality of its

leadership. The interplay between leaders and their teams determines whether the restructuring becomes a period of productive growth or one of paralyzing anxiety, resistance and turnover. A healthy, successful restructuring breeds ambiguity. Effective leaders provide a crystal clear 'why' for the change, tying the new structural framework to a broader organisation mission to enable the employees understand the ultimate goal (Fakhar S et al (2023, Jufrizen J et al , 2021, Ozaze and Chukwuemeka, 2024).

(1) Two-way communication is vital, leaders who actively listen, validate employee concerns, and address grief or fear (like job security) mitigate the negative effects of change.

(2) Role clarity and support; the vacuum created by restructuring can leave employees feeling lost. Leaders must redefine expectations and roles quickly, offering targeted coaching and support to maintain productivity and service delivery.

(3) Cultural alignment: Changing the structural chart without changing the underlying culture often leads to failure. Leaders act as the behavioural anchors, modelling the new cultural norms and demonstrating how the restructured organization will actually operate day-to-day.

Basic Leadership Variables needed when restructuring

The view has been widely canvassed that many have terribly skewed understanding of the concept of what leadership is. Opinions may be divided on this, but we dare to proffer views on some fundamental variables of leadership akin to organizational restructuring.

(i) Leader who is like a priest, it involves standing in the gap. Leaders place their lives on the line for those they lead.

(ii) Leader who is like a minister – service. Thus the leader should behave like a servants, and servants never think of their needs, they rather think first of others. Servants have no personal ambition except to serve and please those they serve. They do not insist on their titles, have no robes of superiority, carry no status symbols, and do not measure their worth by their achievements.

(iii) Leader who has integrity- walking the moral high ground. A good leader should be prepared to go the extra mile, and as Caesar's wife, should be above suspicion. The employees must trust him.

(iv) Leader who is like a modeler – living by example. The creed is 'do as a I do, not just as I say'

(v) Leader who don't just think of promotion, but should understand that it is primarily responsibility.

(vi) Leaders who is mature – in thought, word and action. It is not for mental or physical toddlers.

(vii) Leader who understands that leadership is partnership – with God and with men. It is not for lone rangers. Thus one of the more basic skills of the leader must include team building and healthy interpersonal relations.

(viii) Leader who should know that leadership comes first with a PRICE, before the PRIZE. At times, the prize may even never come in the leader's lifetime. Still he must be prepared to pay the price (Osisioma in Chukwuemeka

2013, Usulor, Chukwuemeka et al , 2024, Ogbonna and Haris 2020)

4. Capacity Building and Organisational Restructuring

Capacity building covers human resource development and the strengthening of managerial systems, institutional development that involves community participation and creation of an enabling environment. Capacity building in the context of organizational development implies a dynamic process which enables employees and agencies to develop the critical social and technical capacities to identify and analyze problems as well as proffer solutions to them. Capacity building also covers the process by which an individual irrespective of sex, are equipped with skills and knowledge they need to perform effectively and efficiently in their different callings. Capacity building could also be defined as the ability to enable the people to make use of their creative potentials intellectual capacities and leadership abilities for personal as well as national growth and development (Sopiah S et al (2021).

Capacity building therefore means planning for employees to acquire knowledge and advanced skills that are critical to organizational development it is the planned programs that will impact skills which will enable the recipient put the knowledge and skills acquired into productive uses to solve wide range of organizational problems. Capacity building from the human capital point of view could be explained to mean when employees possess the needed knowledge and advanced skills that are critical to individual growth and development. The capacity needed by any country for

sustainable development is primarily dependent on the adequacy and relevance of its entrepreneurship.

We therefore advocate that capacity building is central to organizational restructuring. If an organization is restructured without capturing the human side of the enterprise, the process is not complete.

Capacity building is much more than training and includes the following:

(a) Human resource development, the process of equipping individuals with the understanding, skills and access to information, knowledge and training that enables them to perform effectively.

(b) Organization development, the elaboration of management structures, processes and procedures, not only within organizations but also the management of relationships between the different organizations and sectors (public, private and community).

(c) Institutional and legal framework development, making legal and regulatory changes to enable organizations, institutions and agencies at all levels and in all sectors to enhance their capacities

(d) Capacity building is the elements that give fluidity, flexibility and functionality of a program /organization to adapt to changing needs of the population that is served.

(e) It increases the capacity of any developed or developing society to improve trade, employment, economic development and quality of life. It is also true that where institutional capacity is limited, infrastructure development is probably constrained.

5. Employee Empowerment

To empower employees, an organization need to create an environment that encourages autonomy and initiative, in other words, the organization needs to promote psychological safety. This term refers to employee's ability to take a reasonable amount of risk and share opinions without fear of repercussions.

Types of Organizational empowerment

(a) **Individual empowerment** – Is the process of gaining control over your own life,

developing the confidence to make decisions, and taking action to achieve your goals it shifts a person from feeling powerless or dependent to becoming an active self-reliant employee.

(b) **Gender empowerment** – Is the process of enabling the female employees and marginalized-to gain control over their lives, acquire resources, and make meaningful strategic choices. It challenges unequal power structures and ensures everyone has the agency to participate equally in the organization.

Fig 2: Gender empowerment

(c) **Social empowerment** – Is about giving employees more control over their lives in the enterprise. It builds confidence, independence, and access to resources these resources help employees create change. They also support a better future for employees and their environment.

(d) **Educational empowerment** – Is the process of equipping employees with the knowledge, critical thinking skills, and confidence to take control of their own lives and organizational environment. It goes beyond

basic instruction by fostering autonomy, enabling informed decision making and dismantling social or economic barriers.

(e) **Political empowerment** –Is the process by which employees and marginalized groups gain the capacity, confidence, and opportunities to participate effectively in political life. It involves acquiring the resources and authority to influence decisionmaking process and hold leaders accountable.

(f) **Psychological empowerment** –Is a motivational construct reflecting an employee's active orientation toward their environment,

wherein they feel capable, authorized, and in control of shaping their own roles or circumstances. It is commonly understood through for core dimensions

(i) the value placed on a task, goal, or role, driven by an individual's own standards and ideals

(ii) Competence: The belief in one's own capability, skills and self-efficacy to successfully perform task.

(iii) Self-determination: the sense of autonomy and freedom to make choices regarding how and when work is done

(iv) Impact: the belief that one's actions make a real difference and can influence larger operational strategic or environmental outcomes.

(g) Physical empowerment – Is the process of taking control of your physical health, body, and personal safety. It includes developing bodily autonomy, building strength through movement, and acquiring the practical skills needed to feel confident capable, and safe in your everyday life.

Fig 3: *physical exercise (empowerment)*

Core pillars of Physical Empowerment

(i) Physical autonomy and health – understanding your body's needs and having full decision-making power over your physical self. This includes access to quality healthcare, proper nutrition and body positivity.

(ii) Movement and strength training: Using activities like strength training, yoga, or

adaptive sports to enhance endurance, flexibility and physical capability.

(iii) Self-Defense and Personal Safety: Learning the physical and mental skills needed to protect yourself.

6. Automation and Restructuring

Automation and restructuring involve integrating technologies like Artificial Intelligent (AI), and no-code tools to streamline

workflows while reorganizing business operations to improve agility; the transformation requires shifting employees from manual chores toward higher value, strategic roles while addressing operational efficiency.

The Core Components:

(i) Process automation: Utilizing tools like Uipath or Zapier to eliminate redundant tasks,

reduce human error, and accelerate production or service delivery

(ii) Structural reorganization: Changing hierarchical setups (downsizing or down scoping) to boost a tech-enabled workflow, reducing operational silos, and making the organization more agile.

Fig 4: Job loss resulting from automation

With the advent of AI many organizations today are restructuring to adapt and deploy the new technology that will enable their organization boost productivity and service delivery. However, the new technology is not in tandem with the employees aspirations. To employees, the technology has resulted in job loss and low employee intake.

7. Conclusion

Organizational restructuring is one of the most challenging periods for any organization, whether public or private organization. It is therefore imperative that the leadership is mindful of this, and ensure the deployment of all the factors that we have enunciated and interrogated here to create room for efficient and positive restructuring outcome.

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